

FATIGUE LIFE PREDICTION OF CIRCULAR NOTCHED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

J.S. Huh¹, W. Hwang, H.C. Park and K.S. Han
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Pohang University of Science and Technology, Pohang, Korea

ABSTRACT

Fatigue life prediction and fatigue behavior of circular notched carbon fiber reinforced plastic laminates are presented. Point and average stress criteria proposed by Whitney and Nuismer are generalized to fatigue fracture criteria for notched laminates. Residual strength degradation model and the assumptions on the stress redistribution are introduced during the derivation of prediction equations. S-N curve, Basquin's relation, and Hwang and Han's FLPE1 are chosen for evaluation of residual strength of unnotched laminates and six prediction equations are derived. Experiments are performed using Graphite/Epoxy laminates. Presented prediction equations are reasonably close to experimental data and proposed approach is found to be suitable to predict fatigue life of notched composite laminates.

INTRODUCTION

Fatigue phenomena of composite materials are complicated and quite different from those of isotropic materials. The fatigue response of composite laminates with geometric discontinuity such as holes is even more complicated due to the stress concentration and fatigue stress redistribution around holes. The fatigue behavior of circular notched composite laminates should be understood for safer and more efficient design of composite structures. There have been several investigations [1-7] on this topic during the past 15 years. Fatigue delamination initiation was predicted by boundary layer approach [1] and the delamination growth mechanisms were investigated experimentally and analytically [1-6]. The fatigue life and residual strength were also observed [3-6]. It is reported that the residual strength after some fatigue cycles increases and is greater than static notched strength [4-7]. This increase in residual strength is explained that the damage which develops at the hole might reduce the local stress concentration [5]. Yip and Perng [7] suggested stress redistribution equation and predicted the residual strength increase. However, their method can not be used directly in fatigue life prediction of notched laminates. According to their prediction method, fatigue failure will not be occurred because the predicted residual strength increases monotonically with fatigue cycles. So far, no research has been addressed to the fatigue life prediction of notched composite laminates.

In this study, fatigue life prediction of circular notched $[0/\pm 45/90]_n$ graphite/epoxy laminates is investigated. The fatigue failure criteria are suggested using two static notched failure criteria [8] and residual strength degradation model [9]. To derive the fatigue life prediction equations of notched laminates, Yip and Perng's [7] stress redistribution equation is utilized and fatigue life of unnotched laminates are applied to the residual strength degradation. S-N curve, Basquin's relation and Hwang and Han's [10] FLPE (fatigue life prediction equation) 1 are used for fatigue life prediction of unnotched laminates. As a result, six equations are proposed for fatigue life prediction of notched laminates.

¹Present address: Samsung Advanced Institute of Technology, Kihung, Korea

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

Whitney and Nuismer [8] proposed two criteria for predicting the notched strength of the composite materials containing circular holes or cracks. These failure criteria are the point stress criterion and the average stress criterion. They assumed that fracture occurs when the stress at some distance away from the hole reaches the unnotched strength. Point stress criterion is assumed that failure occurs when the stress, σ_y , over a distance, d_o , away from the hole is equal to the unnotched strength

$$\sigma_y(r + d_o, 0) = \sigma_o, \tag{1}$$

where d_o is the characteristic length of point stress criterion and σ_o is tensile strength of unnotched laminates. Average stress criterion is assumed that failure occurs when the average stress over a distance, a_o , away from the hole is equal to the unnotched strength

$$\frac{1}{a_o} \int_r^{r+a_o} \sigma_y(x, 0) dx = \sigma_o, \tag{2}$$

where a_o is the characteristic length of average stress criterion. Fatigue failure condition is essential to predict fatigue life of notched laminates. In this study, the above static failure criteria are considered and modified to analyze fatigue failure of notched laminates. The modification can be made based on the following assumptions.

- 1) Fatigue failure occurs when the stress or average stress under fatigue loading is equal to the residual strength of unnotched laminate.
- 2) The characteristic length is material property and the same both in static fracture and fatigue failure.

Then, the failure criteria under fatigue loading could be expressed

Point Stress Criterion: $\sigma_{yf}(r + d_o, 0) = \sigma_{or}, \tag{3}$

Average Stress Criterion: $\frac{1}{a_o} \int_r^{r+a_o} \sigma_{yf}(x, 0) dx = \sigma_{or}, \tag{4}$

where σ_{yf} is redistributed stress around circular notch due to fatigue loading and σ_{or} is the residual strength of unnotched laminates. The residual strength of unnotched laminates can be expressed as follows [9]:

$$\sigma_{or} = \sigma_o \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_o} \right) \left(\frac{n}{N_{un}} \right) \right], \tag{5}$$

where σ_o is unnotched strength, σ_a is applied stress with considering of area reduction due to notch, n is number of cycles and N_{un} is fatigue life of unnotched laminates. In a specimen with hole size, r and width, w the applied stress has following relation with the nominal stress, $\bar{\sigma}$

$$\sigma_a = \frac{2}{W} \int_r^{w/2} \sigma_y(x, 0) dx = F \bar{\sigma}, \tag{6}$$

where $F = \frac{W}{W - 2r}$.

For an infinite orthotropic plate containing a circular notch of radius r (Figure 1.), the stress along the x -axis can be expressed as follows [11]:

$$\sigma_y^{\infty}(x, 0) = \bar{\sigma} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{r}{x} \right)^2 + \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{r}{x} \right)^4 - \frac{(K_T^{\infty} - 3)}{2} \left(5 \left(\frac{r}{x} \right)^6 - 7 \left(\frac{r}{x} \right)^8 \right) \right], \tag{7}$$

where K_T^{∞} is the stress concentration factor for an infinite plate. Tan [12] modified the above stress distribution for a finite plate using the stress concentration factor for finite plate, K_T , and finite width correction factor. The suggested stress distribution around circular notch for a finite plate can be written

$$\sigma_y(x, 0) = Y \sigma_y^{\infty}(x, 0), \tag{8}$$

where Y is the finite width correction factor,

$$\frac{1}{Y} = \frac{K_T^{\infty}}{K_T} = \frac{1}{2} \left[2 - \left(\frac{2r}{W} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{2r}{W} \right)^4 + (K_T^{\infty} - 3) \left(\frac{2r}{W} \right)^6 \left(1 - \left(\frac{2r}{W} \right)^2 \right) \right]. \tag{9}$$

For quasi-isotropic laminates with circular notch, the stress concentration factor for an infinite plate can be assumed that $K_T^{\infty} = 3$. Then, the stress distribution and finite width correction factor for quasi-isotropic circular notched laminates become

$$\sigma_y(x,0) = Y \bar{\sigma} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{r}{x} \right)^2 + \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{r}{x} \right)^4 \right], \quad (10)$$

and

$$Y = \frac{2}{\left[2 - (2r/W)^2 - (2r/W)^4 \right]}. \quad (11)$$

Figure 1. Plate containing a circular notch under remote uniform tension

It is known that the residual strength increases under cyclic loading [4-7]. Yip and Perng [7] suggested stress redistribution equation and predicted the residual strength increase. Their stress redistribution equation under cyclic loading can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{yf}(x,0) &= \frac{2 \int_r^{W/2} \sigma_y(x,0) dx}{W} + \left(\sigma_y(x,0) - \frac{2 \int_r^{W/2} \sigma_y(x,0) dx}{W} \right) g(n, \sigma_a) \\ &= F \bar{\sigma} + (\sigma_y(x,0) - F \bar{\sigma}) g(n, \sigma_a), \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $g(n, \sigma_a)$ represents the effect of cyclic loading on the stress redistribution and decreases monotonically with number of cycles. Yip and Perng [7] assumed that $g(n, \sigma_a)$ has linear relation with number of cycles, n and is a power function of notch radius, r and nominal average stress, $\bar{\sigma}$. In this study, it is assumed that $g(n, \sigma_a)$ is a power function of number of cycles and applied stress, i.e.

$$g(n, \sigma_a) = 1 - \left(\frac{\log n}{L_o} \right)^\alpha \left(F \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_o} \right)^\beta, \quad (13)$$

where L_o , α and β are material constants and can be evaluated from fatigue tests of notched laminates. Substitution of the above relation into Eqn (12) provides following stress distribution under cyclic loading:

$$\sigma_{yf}(x,0) = F \bar{\sigma} + (\sigma_y(x,0) - F \bar{\sigma}) \left(1 - \left(\frac{\log n}{L_o} \right)^\alpha \left(F \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_o} \right)^\beta \right). \quad (14)$$

The fatigue life prediction of notched laminates can be made by substitution of the above stress distribution relation and residual strength degradation relation of unnotched laminates into fatigue failure criteria. At the number of cycles to failure of notched laminates, N , the residual strength of unnotched laminates is

$$\sigma_{or} = \sigma_o \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_o} \right) \left(\frac{N}{N_{un}} \right) \right] \quad (15)$$

Substitution of the above equation and Eqn (14) into fatigue failure criteria results in following fatigue life prediction equations,

Point Stress Criterion:

$$\sigma_o \left[1 - \left(1 - F \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_o} \right) \frac{N}{N_{un}} \right] = F \bar{\sigma} + (\sigma_y(r + d_o, 0) - F \bar{\sigma}) \left[1 - \left(\frac{\log N}{L_o} \right)^\alpha \left(F \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_o} \right)^\beta \right] \quad (16)$$

Average Stress Criterion:

$$\sigma_o \left[1 - \left(1 - F \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_o} \right) \frac{N}{N_{un}} \right] = F \bar{\sigma} + \left(\frac{1}{a_o} \int_r^{r+a_o} \sigma_y(x, 0) dx - F \bar{\sigma} \right) \left[1 - \left(\frac{\log N}{L_o} \right)^\alpha \left(F \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_o} \right)^\beta \right] \quad (17)$$

Fatigue life of notched laminates under given applied stress can be predicted by the above equations as long as the material constants, fatigue life of unnotched laminates, N_{un} and stress distribution under static loading are known. As mentioned before conventional S-N curve, Basquin's relation and Hwang and Han's [10] FLPE 1 are used for fatigue life prediction of unnotched laminates. Theses equations could be written as follows:

$$\text{S-N curve:} \quad N_{un} = 10^{(\sigma_o/\sigma_o - d)/k} \quad (18.a)$$

where d and k are material constants,

$$\text{Basquin's relation:} \quad N_{un} = (\sigma_a / \sigma_f)^{1/b} / 2, \quad (18.b)$$

where σ_f and b are fatigue strength coefficient and Basquin's exponent, respectively,

$$\text{Hwang and Han's FLPE 1:} \quad N_{un} = \left[M \left\{ 1 - (\sigma_a / \sigma_o)^B \right\} \right]^{1/C} \quad (18.c)$$

where M , B and C are material constants. Substitution of the static stress distribution Eqn (10) and Eqn (18.a) into Eqns (16) and (17) gives following final fatigue life prediction equations of notched laminates;

Point Stress Criterion:

$$\sigma_o \left[1 - \left(1 - F \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_o} \right) \frac{N}{10^{(\sigma_a/\sigma_o - d)/k}} \right] = \bar{\sigma} \left[F + \left(Y \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \xi_1^2 + \frac{3}{2} \xi_1^4 \right) - F \right) \left(1 - \left(\frac{\log N}{L_o} \right)^\alpha \left(F \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_o} \right)^\beta \right) \right] \quad (19)$$

where $\xi_1 = \frac{r}{r + d_o}$,

Average Stress Criterion:

$$\sigma_o \left[1 - \left(1 - F \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_o} \right) \frac{N}{10^{(\sigma_a/\sigma_o - d)/k}} \right] = \bar{\sigma} \left[F + \left(Y \frac{2 - \xi_2^2 - \xi_2^4}{2 - \xi_2} - F \right) \left(1 - \left(\frac{\log N}{L_o} \right)^\alpha \left(F \frac{\bar{\sigma}}{\sigma_o} \right)^\beta \right) \right] \quad (20)$$

where $\xi_2 = \frac{r}{r + a_o}$.

Following the above approaches the other fatigue life prediction equations can be derived and the results are presented in Table 1.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Quasi-isotropic laminate ($[0/\pm 45/90]_s$) was fabricated with unidirectional prepreg tape manufactured by Han Kook Fiber Company. The thickness of laminates was 1 mm while each layer was 0.125 mm in thickness. The width of laminates was 25 mm. A circular hole was made at the center of each specimen using a drilling machine (Figure 2). Five different holes with radii of 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 mm were chosen for static tests. The static strength measurements were conducted at a displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. The specimens with hole radius 1 and 3 mm were chosen for fatigue analysis. The fatigue tests were performed in load control mode using a sinusoidal wave form. The frequency was 4 Hz which is believed to give a negligible temperature rise during tests.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tensile strength of unnotched laminates was found to be 631 MPa. The characteristic length of point stress criterion (P.S.C.) was 0.8035 mm while that of average stress criterion

(A.S.C.) was 2.2225 mm. Static notched strength predictions and experimental data are compared in Figure 3. The results show the better agreement of average stress criterion with experimental data than point stress criterion for this particular material system.

Table 1. Proposed fatigue life prediction equations of circular notched composite laminates

Proposed Life Prediction Equation	
I - 1	<p>Point Stress Criterion - S-N curve</p> $\sigma_o \left[1 - (1 - F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o) (N / 10^{(\sigma_o / \sigma_c - d) / k}) \right]$ $= \bar{\sigma} \left[F + (Y (1 + \xi_1^2 / 2 + 3 \xi_1^4 / 2) - F) (1 - (\log N / L_o)^\alpha (F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o)^\beta) \right]$
I - 2	<p>Point Stress Criterion - Basquin's relation</p> $\sigma_o \left[1 - (1 - F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o) (2N / (\sigma_o / \sigma_f)^{1/b}) \right]$ $= \bar{\sigma} \left[F + (Y (1 + \xi_1^2 / 2 + 3 \xi_1^4 / 2) - F) (1 - (\log N / L_o)^\alpha (F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o)^\beta) \right]$
I - 3	<p>Point Stress Criterion - H and H's FLPE1</p> $\sigma_o \left[1 - (1 - F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o) (N / [M (1 - (\sigma_o / \sigma_o)^\beta)]^{1/c}) \right]$ $= \bar{\sigma} \left[F + (Y (1 + \xi_1^2 / 2 + 3 \xi_1^4 / 2) - F) (1 - (\log N / L_o)^\alpha (F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o)^\beta) \right]$
II - 1	<p>Average Stress Criterion - S-N curve</p> $\sigma_o \left[1 - (1 - F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o) (N / 10^{(\sigma_o / \sigma_c - d) / k}) \right]$ $= \bar{\sigma} \left[F + (Y (2 - \xi_2^2 - \xi_2^4) / (2 - \xi_2) - F) (1 - (\log N / L_o)^\alpha (F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o)^\beta) \right]$
II - 2	<p>Average Stress Criterion - Basquin's relation</p> $\sigma_o \left[1 - (1 - F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o) (2N / (\sigma_o / \sigma_f)^{1/b}) \right]$ $= \bar{\sigma} \left[F + (Y (2 - \xi_2^2 - \xi_2^4) / (2 - \xi_2) - F) (1 - (\log N / L_o)^\alpha (F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o)^\beta) \right]$
II - 3	<p>Average Stress Criterion - H and H's FLPE1</p> $\sigma_o \left[1 - (1 - F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o) (N / [M (1 - (\sigma_o / \sigma_o)^\beta)]^{1/c}) \right]$ $= \bar{\sigma} \left[F + (Y (2 - \xi_2^2 - \xi_2^4) / (2 - \xi_2) - F) (1 - (\log N / L_o)^\alpha (F \bar{\sigma} / \sigma_o)^\beta) \right]$

Figure 2. Test specimen configuration

Figure 3. Static notched strength predicted by point and average stress criteria

Fatigue life predictions of unnotched laminates and experimental data are compared in figure 4. The constants of each equations are estimated by least squares method and the results are presented in table 2. In addition to the figure 4, the residual sum of squares of the applied stress and predicted stresses [$SSR = \sum (\bar{\sigma} - \sigma_{pred})^2$] would give another brief over all comparison though the SSR alone could not determine the superiority of prediction equations. The evaluations of SSR are also presented in table 2. The comparison results show that all three equations seem to predict fatigue life well. It is also found that Hwang and Han's FLPE 1 has smallest SSR among the prediction equations.

Figure 4. Fatigue life prediction curves of unnotched laminates

Table 2. Parameters of fatigue life prediction equations of unnotched composite laminates

FLPE	Parameters			SSR(MPa ²)
S-N curve	$k = -0.0557$	$d = 0.9947$		5167
Basquin's relation	$\sigma_f = 652.33$	$b = -0.0299$		5637
H and H's FLPE1	$M = -3.232$	$B = -5.856$	$C = 0.261$	4578

As mentioned earlier, fatigue life of circular notched composite laminates can be predicted by the equations presented in table 1. The material constants to be determined are reduced to L_o , α and β . The constants are evaluated by fatigue experimental data of notched laminates and least squares method. The evaluation results and SSR are presented in Table 3. The prediction results are compared with experimental data in figures 5 and 6 in case of notch radius 1 and 3 mm, respectively. The comparison shows that the fatigue life of notched composite laminates could be predicted well by the approaches used in this study. The fatigue failure criterion based on A.S.C. predicts fatigue life better than the fatigue failure criterion based on P.S.C. when the notch radius is 1 mm. But we have the opposite result when the notch radius is 3 mm. It is also shown that Eqn II-3 has smallest SSR among the six life prediction equations.

Figure 5. Fatigue test data and predictions of notched laminates ($r = 1\text{mm}$)

Figure 6. Fatigue test data and predictions of notched laminates ($r = 3\text{mm}$)

Table 3. Parameters of fatigue life prediction equations of notched composite laminates

Proposed Fatigue Life Prediction Equation	Parameters			SSR (MPa ²)
	L_o	α	β	
Eqn. I - 1	2.527	30.48	64.03	20855
Eqn. I - 2	2.384	37.99	87.65	26831
Eqn. I - 3	4.102	80.00	69.97	80546
Eqn. II - 1	2.504	23.70	50.30	13377
Eqn. II - 2	1.968	15.56	43.73	18004
Eqn. II - 3	2.652	20.48	39.18	10197

CONCLUSION

Based on Whitney and Nuismer's static failure criteria, fatigue failure criteria for predicting fatigue life of circular notched composite laminates are proposed using residual strength degradation model and the assumptions on the stress redistribution. Six equations for predicting fatigue life of circular notched composite laminates have been formulated using the fatigue failure criteria and fatigue life equations of unnotched laminates. It is found that proposed FLPEs have good agreements with fatigue experimental data of circular notched composite laminates.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was partially supported by Korea Science and Engineering Foundation under Grant 91-0200-07-04-3.

REFERENCES

1. L. Ye, "Characteristics of Delamination Growth in a Notched Graphite/Epoxy Composite Laminate," *J. Reinf. Plast. and Comp.*, **8**, 79-89 (1989).
2. M. Beghine, M. Bertini, and L. Vitale, "Analysis of Fatigue Delamination Growth in Carboresin Specimens with Central Hole," *Comp. Struc.*, **17**, 257-274 (1991).
3. A. Razvan, C. E. Bakis, and K. L. Reifsnider, "Influence of Load Levels on Damage Growth Mechanisms of Notched Composite Materials," *ASTM STP 1059*, 371-389 (1990).
4. J. D. Whitcomb, "Experimental and Analytical Study of Fatigue Damage in Notched Graphite/Epoxy Laminates," *ASTM STP 723*, 48-63 (1981).
5. G. R. Kress and W. W. Stinchcomb, "Fatigue Response of Notched Graphite/Epoxy Laminates," *ASTM STP 864*, 173-196 (1985).
6. C. E. Bakis, R. A. Simonds, L. W. Vick, and W. W. Stinchcomb, "Matrix Toughness, Long-Term Behavior, and Damage Tolerance of Notched Graphite Fiber-Reinforced Composite Materials," *ASTM STP 1059*, 349-370 (1990).
7. M. C. Yip and T. B. Perng, "The Influence of Hole Size in Static Strength and Fatigue for CFRP Composite Materials," *Proc. Inter. Conf. on Adv. Comp. Mater.*, 651-657 (1993).
8. J. M. Whitney and R. J. Nuismer, "Stress Fracture Criteria for Laminated Composites Containing Stress Concentrations," *J. Comp. Mater.*, **8**, 253-265 (1974).
9. L. J. Broutman and S. Sahu, "A New Theory to Predict Cumulative Fatigue Damage in Fiberglass Reinforce Plastics," *ASTM STP 497*, 170-188 (1972).
10. W. Hwang and K. S. Han, "Fatigue of Composite Materials - Damage Model and Life Prediction," *ASTM STP 1012*, 88-102 (1989).
11. H. J. Konish and J. M. Whitney, "Approximate Stresses in an Orthotropic Plate Containing a Circular Hole," *J. Comp. Mater.*, **9**, 157-166 (1975).
12. S. C. Tan, "Finite-Width Correction Factors for Anisotropic Plate Containing a Central Opening," *J. Comp. Mater.*, **22**, 1080-1097 (1988).